

TYPES OF MURAL ART

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the types of mural art, the restoration of cultural and spiritual heritage today, Afro-Siberian murals, the rhythmic repetition of the same image several times.

Key words: mural art, spiritual heritage, cultural heritage, mural paintings.

Introduction:

Today, restoration and wide promotion of cultural and spiritual heritage, application of the results of innovative research in the field of history and science to the educational process, textbooks and educational literature, creation of a new generation of textbooks, and talented young people for scientific research engagement is of the utmost importance.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The socio-economic changes of the early Middle Ages did not leave an impact on the culture of Central Asia. Although the cultural life of this period developed on the basis of the cultural traditions of antiquity, the emergence of several independent states and estates in the ruins of the Kushan state made possible the emergence of unique local cultures. At the same time, relations with neighboring countries, primarily India, Iran, Afghanistan, China, and nomadic herders were also important for the formation of the culture of the early Middle Ages.

Afro-Syob wall paintings — Afro-Syob is one of the rare examples of majestic paintings found as a result of archeological excavations. The first samples were discovered by archaeologist V. Vyatkin (1913). During the subsequent excavations, Uzbek archaeologists managed to open about 30 palace rooms, many of these rooms were decorated with murals and patterns. Of these, the paintings in the large and small rooms are relatively well preserved.

Results:

In one of the rooms, a man and a woman are depicted sitting in front of an arch. The paintings on the walls of the large room are significant for their richness of details and preserved Sugdian inscriptions. The paintings on the walls of the room depict the wedding ceremony, the reception of the ambassadors of foreign countries by the ruler of Sughd, the adventures of these ambassadors on the road, encounters with wild animals, hunting scenes, and mythical creatures. The analysis of preserved paintings allows to think about the ideological artistic direction of the medieval fine art, the artist's working methods and tools, detailed household scenes, ethnic scenes of that period.

The artist divided the wall into 3 parts, separated the 2 outer parts with a narrow pattern border, worked on the main part with a thematic image, reflected the events as if watching from above. The wall paintings of Afrosyab are subordinated to a single content: in the center stands the ruler of Sughd, Varkhuman, according to tradition, the artist depicts him in a larger view than others, recognizing the greatness of the ruler, giving him eternity and heroism.

Discussion:

Rhythmic repetition of the same image several times is characteristic of these images. If the picture is divided into four equal parts by straight lines and a diagonal line is drawn, the compositional arrangement of the image will be clearly visible. In it, it is seen that the geese are divided into four parts and are arranged in a specific rhythmic basis. Another artistic solution of the photo is that along the upper and lower horizons, two geese are looking at the same roof, and two single geese are in the opposite position.

In the image, it seems as if two pairs of geese are entering the picture, and two separately depicted geese are leaving it. The above analyzes show that from the time of the Old Kingdom, fine art was created on the basis of clear compositional laws.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that Afrosiyab wall paintings show the development of majestic painting in Central Asia before the Arab conquest, and that Samarkand was its center. In the murals, it is observed that not only formal images are used, but also free themes. For example, the relief image "Cranes" belonging to the 5th dynasty in Saqqara and the wall image "Geese" in the Medume saga can be noted here. The group of birds is expressed in a unique decorative way in the images.

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